

Integrated pest management – insects

Rice grain yield loss due to rice hispa damage

P. B. Chatterjee and P. K. Bera, Rice Research Station, P.O. Chinsurah R.S. 712102, West Bengal, India

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier appears sporadically in West Bengal ricefields. In favorable years, infestation starts on summer or boro rice and spreads to wetland (aman) rice. In most cases, population buildup and dispersal are aggregated.

We studied yield loss caused by rice hispa in an IR36 crop in boro. The crop suffered repeated waves of rice hispa

attack, beginning with transplanting in mid-Jan to harvest in Apr. Highly irregular patterns of damage were visible as white lesions in leaves. We marked 10 samples of 1 m² each that exhibited 5-80% leaf area damage. Undamaged samples were also marked. Each sample contained 35 hills.

Individual samples were separately harvested, threshed, and weighed. Yield loss caused by rice hispa in a short-duration variety like IR36 was negatively correlated ($r = 0.9927387^{**}$) with increase in leaf area damaged, and correspondingly less grain yield was recorded (see figure). ■

Effect of different degrees of rice hispa attack on grain yield.

Behavior of the wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Boes. et Str.)

W. L. Morrill, Entomology Research Laboratory, Montana State University, Bozeman, Montana 59717, USA; and E. G. Rubia, Entomology Department, IRR1

L. pseudoannulata is a common spider in wetland ricefields. Unlike other species, the wolf spider can hide under water. We have observed silver bubbles covering the body of a wolf spider under water. Perhaps hairs present all over the body of the spider trap air films for a period of time, allowing the spider to breathe.

We studied the factors that enable *L. pseudoannulata* to hide under water. A 35-d-old TN1 potted rice plant was placed in a 35- × 25- × 30-cm aquarium half-filled with water and covered with nylon mesh. Spiders at different stages were released one at a time and subjected to the following conditions: light change, splashing water, plant movement, and physical injury.

For light change, the aquarium was covered with black muslin for 5 min, then the cloth was slowly removed. The change from darkness to light did not affect the spiders, except for a female carrying an egg sac and a spiderling (see table). These moved up near the junction of the leaves and stems.

Time spent under water by *Lycosa pseudoannulata*.^a

Condition	Time range (min)		
	Spiderling	Adult	
		Male	Female
Light change	0	0	0
Splashing water	0	0	0
Tapping rice plant	0	0	2.35-13.09
Physical injury	1.33-10.15	-	3.25- 8.59

^an=12.

Splashing water on the rice plant caused all spiders to move up and down the rice plant or away from the rice plant, if they were hit by water. This has also been observed in ricefields during spider collection.

Tapping the rice plant caused early-instar spiderlings and newly molted male spiders to move up and down the rice plant or to hide at the base in between tillers. A female spider carrying an egg sac went under water 4 out of 11 times the plant was tapped. Duration of her stay under water ranged from 3 to 13 min.

Pinching a leg using forceps caused a newly molted male and a female with egg sac to go under water for 1-10 min.

The underwater hiding behavior explains why some sampling methods, such as D-vac, are not efficient in collecting the wolf spider in ricefields. Air coming from a D-vac machine

disturbs the canopy and the spiders dive. The FARMCOP sampling device does not disturb the spiders so much, although sometimes we had to wait for spiders to emerge. ■

Alternate plant hosts of rice leaffolder (LF)

L. R. Bharati, Hari Om, and K. S. Kushwaha, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul 132021 Haryana, India

LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) was a minor and sporadic pest in Haryana until 1986. Epidemics occurred in 1987 and 1989 wet seasons.

Annual or perennial plant habitats that influence LF number are important in understanding epidemic patterns. It is also essential to establish the relative suitability of wild or cultivated hosts that contribute to LF carryover from Nov to May, when rice is not grown, as a basis for a sound integrated pest management strategy.

The normal cropping pattern in the region is rice - wheat. We found that rice LF could survive winter on wheat. Under fluctuating temperatures in the screen-house (max 23.5 °C and min 8.7 °C with 4-30 °C range) from Nov to the first week of Mar, rice LF completed one generation